

Evaluation of Indications of Colostomy and Study its Complication**Mithilesh Kumar¹, Kundan Kumar², Sushant Kumar Sharma³**¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar²Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar³Professor, Department of General Surgery, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** A colostomy is a surgically created opening, or stoma, in the colon, the large intestine. The purpose of this study is to assess colostomy indications and examine associated complications.**Methods:** From February to July of 2024, a prospective study was conducted in the general surgery department of Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital in Muzaffarpur, Bihar. This study comprised 118 patients who had colostomies performed in an emergency or elective setting for any reason.**Results:** Of the 118 cases, males (n = 87 out of 74%) and females (n = 31 out of 118) (26%), were the most usually affected. Thirty-one percent (n=35 out of 118) of the cases were in the age group of 51 to 60. Intestinal blockage (n=28, 23.7%) was the most frequent reason for colostomy development, followed by cancer (n=55, 46.6%). 54 patients, or 46.4% of the total number of colostomy patients, had problems. The study revealed that 25% of the complications were local sepsis, 7% were prolapse, 4% were retraction, 4% were necrosis, 1.6% were parastomal hernia, 1.6% were stenosis, 1.6% were intestinal obstruction, and 1.6% were bleeding.**Conclusion:** The most frequent reason for a colostomy is carcinoma of the colon and rectum. The most frequent side effect is local sepsis.**Keywords:** Stoma, Colon, Hernia, Sepsis.

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Introduction

Over 200 years have passed since the creation of the first surgical stoma. The Greek word for mouth or opening is where the word "stoma" originates. An intestinal stoma is a surgically created opening in the front abdominal wall. In 1970, Littre of Paris performed the first ventral colostomy for a youngster who had an imperforate anus. Stomas are utilized to relieve obstruction in an emergency and to redirect the faecal stream away from the distal intestine to allow a distal anastomosis to heal. There are several reasons why intestinal stomas arise. The conditions that might cause ulcerative colitis include intestinal blockage, cancer of the colon and rectum, Crohn's disease, congenital bowel defects, large intestine bleeding that cannot be stopped, intestinal trauma, inflammatory and ischemic bowel diseases, bladder cancer, and spinal cord injuries.

Even while stomas are a life-saving treatment, they come with a lot of complications, lead to social isolation, and significantly lower quality of life. The first stomas were in fact inadvertent enterocutaneous fistulas brought on by puncturing

abdominal wounds or intestinal illness complications such as incarcerated hernias. Following surgery, patients undergoing stoma creation are susceptible to a variety of complications. Numerous factors, including high body mass index, inflammatory bowel illness, use of steroids and immunosuppressive medicines, diabetes mellitus, advanced age, emergency surgery, surgical procedures, and surgeon expertise, have been linked to an increased risk of stoma complications. The aim of our study is to evaluate indications of colostomy and study its complication.

Materials and Methods

From February to July of 2024, the Department of General Surgery at Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital in Muzaffarpur, Bihar, conducted this prospective study.

This study comprised 118 patients who had colostomies performed in an emergency or elective setting for any reason. Information was collected from patient case files and operated notes that were kept on file by the department of surgery.

These cases were examined to assess the types, indications, and complications associated with colostomies.

All patients male and female between 1-70 years and elective cases undergoing intestinal stoma

construction were included in this study. Patients undergoing urinary stoma construction and indication for gynaecological disorders were excluded in this study.

Results

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age group (years)	No. of cases	Percentage
1-10	12	10%
11-20	9	7.6%
21-30	13	11%
31-40	24	20.3%
41-50	11	9.3%
51-60	35	30%
>60	14	11.8%
TOTAL	118	100%

In our study Maximum number of cases were in 51 to 60 age group (n=35 out of 118) 30% followed by 31 to 40 age group (n=24) table 1.

Table 2: Sex distribution

Sex	No. of cases	Percentage
Female	31	26%
Male	87	74%
Total	118	100%

In our study Males (n=87 out of 118) were commonly affected then female (n=31 out of 118)26% table 2.

Table 3: Elective Vs emergency

Elective	Emergency
13	105
11%	89%

In our study 105(89%) stomas are made in emergency setting and in 13(11%) were made in routine table 3.

Table 4: Indications

Indications	Number of stomas	Percentage
Carcinoma colon and rectum	55	46.6%
Intestinal obstruction	28	23.7%
Abdominal trauma	16	13.6%
Ano rectal malformation	10	8.5%
Sigmoid volvulus	4	3.4%
Hirschprung disease	3	2.5%
High fistula in ano	2	1.7%
TOTAL	118	100%

In our study the most common indication for colostomy formation was carcinoma (n=55, 46.6%), followed by intestinal obstruction (n=28, 23.7%) followed by abdominal trauma (n=16, 13.6%), followed by anorectal malformation(n=10, 8.5%), followed by sigmoid volvulus (n=4, 3.4%) followed by hirschprung disease (n=3, 2.5%), followed by high fistula in ano(n=2, 1.7%) table 4.

Table 5: Types of stoma

Procedure	Numbers	Percentage
Sigmoid colostomy	78	66%
Loop colostomy	33	28%
End colostomy	7	6%
TOTAL	118	100%

In our study the most commonly performed colostomy is the sigmoid colostomy 66%, followed by the loop colostomy 28% and least is end colostomy 6% table 5.

Table 6: Complication

Complication	Number	Percentage
Local sepsis	30	25%
Prolapse	9	7%
Retraction	5	4%
Necrosis	5	4%
Parastomal hernia	2	1.6%
Stenosis	2	1.6%
Intestinal obstruction	2	1.6%
Bleeding	2	1.6%
Electrolyte imbalance	0	0%
Total	57	46.4%

In colostomy patients total n=57 complications were observed in 54 patients that is 46.4% of patients. In our study the complication were reported as Local sepsis 25%, Prolapse 7%, Retraction 4%, Necrosis 4%, Parastomal hernia 1.6%, Stenosis 1.6%, Intestinal obstruction 1.6%, Bleeding 1.6% table 6.

Discussion

Taking into account the various data from literature and comparing it with present series a few interesting fact is come into lime light.

Maximum number of cases were in 51 to 60 age group (n=35 out of 118) 30%. Males (n=87 out of 118) were commonly affected then female (n=31 out of 118)26%. While study conducted by P. Sumathi et al [6]. Showed maximum number of patients was in the age group of 55 to 65 year (n=32 out of 50) and males (n=36 out of 50) are more commonly affected than females (n=14). While study conducted by Ahmad Z et al [15] showed out of 100, 70 were males and 30 were females. The mean age group was 50.5 ± 29.01 year with a range of 12 to 85 year.

In our study 105 (89%) stomas are made in emergency setting and in 13(11%) were made in routine. While in study conducted by Ahmad Z et al [15] showed 97 stomas were made in emergency and 3 stoma were made in routine. The most common indication for colostomy formation was carcinoma (n=55, 46.6%), followed by intestinal obstruction (n=28, 23.7%) followed by abdominal trauma (n=16, 13.6%), followed by anorectal malformation (n=10, 8.5%), followed by sigmoid volvulus (n=4, 3.4%) followed by hirschprung disease (n=3, 2.5%), followed by high fistula in ano (n=2, 1.7%). Study conducted by P.Sumathi et al [6] showed the most common indication for stoma were carcinoma followed by abdominal trauma.

In our study the most commonly performed colostomy is the sigmoid colostomy 66%, followed by the loop colostomy 28% and least is end colostomy 6%.while study conducted by P. Sumathi et al [6] showed the most common stoma created was colostomy n=41 out of 50. Same study

showed total 41 patients underwent colostomy formation of which 22 were end colostomy and 19 were transverse loop colostomy.

While study conducted by Ahmad Z et al [15] showed, the most common stoma was loop ileostomy followed by sigmoid colostomy, followed by transverse loop colostomy with most of them being formed in males 76%. Similar in a study by Shah JN et al [11] loop ileostomy was the most common stoma formed (70%) followed by loop colostomy (17%). Ileostomy accounted for 70% stomas in another study by Ghazi MA et al [7] followed by colostomy in 30%. In a study by Safirullah et al [3] loopileostomy was formed in 43% cases and loop colostomy in 17.4% of cases.

In colostomy patients total n=57 complications were observed in 54 patients that is 46.4% of patients. In our study the complication were reported as Local sepsis 25%, Prolapse 7%, Retraction 4%, Necrosis 4%, Parastomal hernia 1.6%, Stenosis 1.6%, Intestinal obstruction 1.6%, Bleeding 1.6%. The local sepsis complication were commonly seen in study conducted by P. Sumathi et al [6] in the form of chemical dermatitis and folliculitis occur in patients undergone end colostomy. In all of them, major was a lack of proper seal around stoma and stoma bag. All of them were treated by applying a colostomy paste which formed a protective barrier over the skin. Use of a skin sealent with a copolymer or plasticizing agent without alcohol provide a thin protective film on the skin surface helps prevent skin stripping of the epidermis during adhesive removal and as a moisture barrier.

The most common complication reported in Ahmad Z et al[15] was peristomal skin irritation and erythema(36%) followed by laparotomy wound infection (13.4%) and peristomal skin infection, abscess formation and fistula formation(8.1%). A study by Ratliff et al [4] has shown peristomal irritation in 53% cases, while Pearl et al [5] showed peristomal erythema as the most common complication in 42%. Ambreenmuneer [14] reported skin excoriation in 18% cases. Safirullah et al [3] reported skin erythema in 12% followed by

prolapse 6% and retraction 4%. In study conducted by P. Sumathi et al [6] showed loop colostomy tends to prolapse more than colostomy and proximal more than distal. Then necrosis was observed in 5% of patients and found in immediate post-operative period. It requires laparotomy and revision of stoma.

Conclusion

While stomal complications are a new risk factor for death, other well-established prognostic factors are thought to have a greater impact. Age, the urgency of a surgical procedure, and the diagnosis are so found to affect morbidity and death.

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